

ROLE OF RAHU IN HINDU ASTROLOGY

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Abstract:

In this paper the characters of Rahu and the professions influenced by Rahu are explained. Yogam given by Rahu and Dosham given by Rahu are detailedly explained. Rahu standing house from lagna to twelfth house predictions are given elaborately. According to Pulippani astrology predictions of Rahu standing bhava, from lagna to twelfth bhava are given exactly.

Key Words: Characters of Rahu - Professions given by Rahu - Yogam by Rahu - Dosham by Rahu - Saturn with Rahu - Rahu standing house and prediction - prediction of Rahu standing bhava according to Pulippani astrology.

Characters of Rahu:

Rahu is the serpent planet. It is called as black snake. It moves reverse direction, Rahu represents materialism, mischief, fear, dissatisfaction, obsession and confusion. Rahu is also associated with science and occultism. Rahu is an enemy against the Sun and the Moon. It is generally. Considered as a malefic planet. It takes 18 months to move from one sign to another. Rahu is considered as a planet which induces laziness, delays and hurdles in work.

Professions, given by Rahu:

In ones horoscope Rahu stands in third / sixth / tenth or eleventh bhava the following professions or business is apt for them. There are illegal business, wine shop business, gambling casino, black money, abused drugs, magician, black magic, astrologer, international import and export, blue metals, mines, natural gas & oil, explosive goods, weapon making cinema, tele communication, medical field, chemical engineering, X-ray, CT scan, M.R.I.Scan, and smuggling. Without physical effort easily they earn money more and more. But very soon their money would go from them.

Yogam given by Rahu:

There are so many yogas given by Rahu. There are Parvatha yogam, Kodeeswara yogam, Sarppa yogam & Kothanda yogam.

Parvatha Yogam:

Rahu stands in Aries / Taurus / Cancer / Virgo or Capricorn with any one planet with it. And also one planet must stand in Kendra place (1/4/7/10) from Rahu, One could enjoy parvatha yogam. It gives rajayogam (live as the king)

Kodeeswara Yogam:

Rahu stands in Aries / cancer / Libra or capricorn without any planet. At that time Kethu must conjunction with Jupiter. And also Mercury or Venus should stand ninth house from Rahu or Kethu. This kind of people take name as a multi millionaire in his / her life. They should donate money for social service.

Sarppa Yogam:

Rahu stands in first / fourth / seventh or tenth house from lagna it is called as sarppa yogam. If it is aspected by Jupiter / Venus or Mercury it gives raja yogam (live as a king)

Kothanda Yogam:

If Rahu stands in Sagittarius at is called kothanda yogam. Who born under this yoga would be a very very important person (VVIP) in the world. They have no enemies. Their all efforts give success easily.

Dosham given by Rahu:

Before or After Moon:

Rahu Stands before or after Moon it gives great dosham. One could suffer a lot. One should face more dangers in their life during Rahu dasha or bukthi and also Moon dasha or bukthi.

Divorce Dosham:

If Rahu stands in lagna or second house one should do his / her marriage after the age 30. Other wise one should get separation from his/her spouse (life partner).

Example Chart:

Date of Birth	:	10.03.1980
Time of Birth	:	06.02 pm

Place of Birth : Tirunelveli
 Birth Star : Moolam
 Ascendent : Leo

8	Venus	10	11
Sun Mercury Kethu	RASI D1		12
6			Rahu Mars Jupiter ASC
Moon	4	3	Saturn

Merc	Moon	Rahu Sun	Mars Jupiter
5	NAVAMSA D9		Venus
4			11
3	Kethu	ASC	12

Kethu Dasa Balance: 5 years 5 Months 27 days

The native got married at the age of 25 and got divorce

Pulthira Dosham:

If Rahu stands in first / fifth or ninth trine it gives child issues, abortion and delay of children. The native will get child after the age of 40 by remedy parihar pooja.

Example Chart:

Date of Birth : 21.08.1976
 Time of Birth : 07.42 pm
 Place of Birth : Madurai
 Birth Star : Arudhra
 Ascendent : Aquaris

2	Kethu	Jupiter	Moon
ASC	RASI D1		Saturn
12			Sun Venus
11	10	Rahu	Merc Mars

11	12	Sun ASC	2
Jupiter Moon Mars Rahu	NAVAMSA D9		3
Mercury			Kethu
8	Saturn	Venus	5

Rahu dasa balance : 5 years 6 months

26 days

The native got child at the age of 42.

Saturn with Rahu Conjunction:

It gives famous in the field of computer, detective agency. Foreign affairs, emphassy, drugs abuse, pesticides, fertilizers black magic, bomb making, CT scan, MRI scan, X-ray, mines and smuggling. They should reach high status in society after the age of 35.

Rahu Stands in Lagna:

It Rahu stands in lagna one should become a rich man suddenly. But he has no formal education. He should be a popular person in society.

Rahu Stands in Second House:

If Rahu stands in second house one should be a miser. One has no joyful family life. It gives illegal affairs. One should affect by black magic.

Rahu Stands in Third House:

If Rahu stands in third house it is very auspicious one. The native could do everything successful. Family members always help him/her. Because this is called upajayasthanam.

Rahu Stands in Fourth House:

If Rahu stands in fourth house the native should lead always healthy life. The native should face some problems by ladies. Their family life is always happy.

Rahu Stands in Fifth House:

If Rahu stands in fifth house the native is helped by his/her friends than relatives. By the supports of friends he / she should complete his / her task successfully.

Rahu Stands in Sixth House:

If Rahu stands in sixth house upajayasthana one should shine in music/drama or movie. Military and Medicine professions gives name and fame. Happiness comes from spouse and kids.

Rahu Stands in Seventh House:

If Rahu stands in seventh house one should suffer a lot. One should attract by black magic. Divorce will be expected from the spouse.

Rahu Stands in Ninth House:

If Rahu stands in ninth house one should enjoy the life very well. Elders will support them. They are always rich. They will be honoured by the government.

Rahu Stands in Tenth House:

If Rahu stands in tenth house family life would be bitter. But it gives high position in job. Money flows very well. One should buy lot of properties. One should shine in own business. Because it is (tenth house) Upajayasthana.

Rahu Stands in Eleventh House:

If Rahu stands in eleventh house one should face love failure but win in share market, casino and lottery. Because it is upajayasthana. One should do so many business very well.

Rahu Stands in Twelfth House:

If Rahu stands in twelfth house one should make friendship with bad fellows. One should spend lot of money for evil matters. The native should expect help from their relatives.

Predictions According to Pulippani Astrology:

Rahu Stands in Lagna:

If Rahu stands in lagna bhava (first house) One should face difficulties in child issue. One should affect by leprosy. One should aware to safe from snakes.

Rahu Stands in Second House:

If Rahu stands in second house one should always speak filthy words. One should love black magic one should be a fool. One should not have money.

Rahu Stands in Third House:

If Rahu stands in third house (Upajayasthana) the native has long life. The native will be praised by all. There is no help from brothers.

Rahu Stands in Fourth House:

If Rahu stands in fourth house it is danger to mother's health. The native should be lazy. They will be hated by their relatives. Native place should not favour.

Rahu Stands in Fifth House:

If Rahu stands in fifth house. One should have only female child the native do black magic and do all evil matters. The native have no blessings of their family diety.

Rahu Stands in Sixth House:

If Rahu stands in sixth house (Upajayasthana) one should win all his/her enemies. One have excellent spouse. One have the best home. It is very auspicious one.

Rahu Stands in Seveth House:

If Rahu stands in Seveth house one should make intercourse with many persons. One should spend their more time to enjoy with other gender. The family life doesn't give pleasure.

Rahu Stands in Eighth House:

If Rahu stands in eighth house one should be bite by snakes One should suffer for money. Life partner's separation is unavoidable.

Rahu Stands in Ninth House:

If Rahu stands in ninth house One's ancestors did so many sins and crimes. The native should learn black magic.

Rahu Stands in Tenth House:

If Rahu stands in tenth house (Upajayasthana) one should marry so many spouse. But the native has noble qualities.

Rahu Stands in Eleventh House:

If Rahu stands in eleventh house (Upajayasthana) one should get benefits from government side. The native's fifth house would be affected by kethu. So, child born would be delayed.

Rahu Stands in Twelfth House:

If Rahu stands in twelfth house one should go to foreign countries. Easily the native would be affected by foot disease. His/her wealth would be spoilt.

Saturn and Rahu Conjunction:

The above conjunction give fame in detective agency, embassy and foreign affairs. This conjunction is apt for bomb makers, black magicians, snake hunters, smugglers and illegal business doers. This conjunction is called "kulami yoga". These type of people's first half life is very difficult. Later, after the age of 35 the native will improve their life with self help (Own effort).

Conclusion:

Role of Rahu in Indian astrology takes a vital part. Though Rahu is a shadow planet and also has no own house. It's position in our horoscope is very important. During the marriage matching Rahu plays an important role. We should worship Prathyangira Devi and Karudazhwar to reduce the evil effects of Rahu.

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